

Synthesis of some new metal(II) polychelates

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Bis(mercaptoacetamido)-4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (BMADM) and its polychelates with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have been synthesized. The polychelates show semiconducting behavior. The value of activation energy lies in the range 0.479–1.123 eV.

Polymeric metal complexes show interesting and important characteristics, especially in areas such as semiconductors¹, heat resistance materials² and molecular recognition³. In construction of one to three-dimensional framework multidentate ligands are usually used to bridge metal centers to form polymeric structures. For instance, metal-organic framework based on 4,4'-bipyridine or polycarboxylic acids have extensively been studied⁴. In the light of above facts, we report here the synthesis of bis(mercaptoacetamido)-4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (BMADM) and its polychelates with Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II}. The structures of the polychelates have been established by analytical, magnetic, IR and electronic spectral data. The d.c. electrical conductivity has also been studied.

Results and discussion

All the metal chelates (Table 1) are dark coloured solids, stable to air and non-hygroscopic. They are insoluble in almost all common organic solvents and decompose at high temperature without melting. Elemental analyses suggest 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry to these polychelates.

IR spectrum of the ligand exhibits a medium intensity band at 3330 cm⁻¹ due to amido group. This band is shifted to lower frequency by 15–20 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the polychelates, indicating coordination of amido nitrogen to the metal ion⁵. The ligand band at 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=O) appears at the same frequency in all the polychelates, suggesting the non-involvement of oxygen of C=O on complexation⁶. The ligand exhibits a sharp band at 2660 cm⁻¹ (SH). Absence of this band in the spectra of the polychelates indicates coordination through thiolic sulfur to the metal after deprotonation. This is further supported

Table 1. Analytical and electrical conductivity data of BMADM polychelates*

Compd.	Metal % : Found (Calcd.)	σ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Activation energy eV
[Mn ^{II} (BMADM)] _n	14.89 (15.94)	6.536×10^{-5}	0.479
{[Co ^{II} (BMADM)].2H ₂ O} _n	12.82 (13.41)	1.130×10^{-2}	0.670
[Ni ^{II} (BMADM).2H ₂ O] _n	11.89 (12.85)	1.630×10^{-5}	0.650
{[Cu ^{II} (BMADM)].H ₂ O} _n	13.88 (14.91)	1.481×10^{-3}	0.626
[Zn ^{II} (BMADM).2H ₂ O] _n	13.69 (14.66)	9.673×10^{-5}	0.993
[Cd ^{II} (BMADM)] _n	23.91 (24.60)	4.148×10^{-3}	1.123

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. ^aAt 373 K.

by a downward shift (~10 cm⁻¹) of S-CH₂ from 1400 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the polychelates⁷. In the far-IR region, the additional medium bands are observed at 460–500 (M-N) and 340–360 cm⁻¹ (M-S)⁷. The broad bands around 3450 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the polychelates except Mn^{II} and Cd^{II}, may be due to ν_{OH} vibrations of water molecules.

The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} chelate shows bands at 9009, 16666, and 19048 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, suggestive of octahedral geometry around the Ni^{II} ion⁸. The Ni^{II} chelate has magnetic moment 3.04 B.M. which is close to the range observed for octahedral complexes⁹. In addition to a charge transfer band at 38561 cm⁻¹, two more bands have been observed for the Mn^{II} chelate at 19094 and 22608 cm⁻¹ assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_1(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$ and ${}^6A_1(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_2(G)$, respectively, considering a tetrahedral geometry¹⁰. The experimental magnetic moment value (5.65 B.M.) is slightly different from those calculated but which is within the range for high-spin Mn^{II} ions with tetrahedral geometry⁵. The magnetic moment of the Co^{II} polychelate is found to be 2.98 B.M., which is well within the range expected for square-planar Co^{II} complexes^{10,11}. The electronic spectrum of the

Co^{II} chelate exhibits two bands at 16584 and 17731–23255 cm^{-1} attributed to ${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2A_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively, in square-planar geometry¹². The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} chelate shows bands at 16584, 18974 and 23256 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and C.T. transitions, respectively, consistent with square-planar geometry¹³. The observed magnetic moment (1.80 B.M.) is slightly higher than the one calculated for one unpaired electron; however, the electronic spectra and magnetic moment are suggestive of a square-planar geometry for Cu^{II} ion¹⁴. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} chelates are found to be diamagnetic as expected for d^{10} -configuration and have octahedral and tetrahedral geometry, respectively, on the basis of analytical and IR spectral data¹⁵.

The electrical conductivity of all the chelates was studied over a wide range of temperature. The dependence of the electrical conductivity on temperature is expressed by the equation: $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, where σ_0 is a constant, E_a the activation energy of conduction process, T the absolute temperature and k the Boltzman constant. The values of electrical conductivity (σ) lie in the range of typical semiconductor¹⁶. The logarithm of the conductivity is plotted against reciprocal of the absolute temperature and a linear relationship has been observed. In the present study, temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity exhibits two distinct regions (Fig. 1). In low temperature region the slopes of the plots have small values. This may be due to extrinsic conduction present in them, whereas in the high temperature region, a linear dependence with high value of $\log \sigma = f(10^3/T)$ is observed. In this temperature domain, these polychelates may behave as intrinsic semiconductors. This phase transition observed is most probably associated with two molecular structures of the ligand (keto-enol form), which exchange the conduction at different thermal stabilities. In low temperature range, the conduction is due to the excitation of carrier from donor localized level to the conduction band, while at the upper temperature range, the intrinsic region is reached where carriers are thermally activated from the valence band to conduction band¹⁷. This behavior can be attributed to interaction between the electrons of d -orbitals of metal and π -orbitals of the ligand at upper temperature range¹⁶. This interaction will lead to localized action of π -electronic charge on the ligand which leads to increased the activation energy¹¹. The conductivity of the polychelates at 373 K decreases in the order: $\text{Co} > \text{Cd} > \text{Cu} > \text{Zn} > \text{Mn} > \text{Ni}$. It is observed that there is no significant difference between the activation energy values obtained for various polychelates. This is consistent with the earlier conclusion that the mechanism of conduction is of similar type in all cases.

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of $\log \sigma$ of BMADM chelate polymers: (■) Cu^{II} , (□) Cd^{II} , (▲) Zn^{II} , (●) Ni^{II} , (△) Co^{II} , (○) Mn^{II} .

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. DMF and ethanol were used after distillation.

The ligand (BMADM) was prepared by the condensation of mercaptoacetic acid and 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane. Mercaptoacetic acid (0.2 mol) in methanol (25 ml) in presence of a few drops of H_2SO_4 was refluxed on a water-bath for 45 min. Then a solution of 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (0.1 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was added to it with stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. On cooling, the resulting pale cream coloured solid was washed with water and methanol, and crystallized. The purity of the ligand was checked by TLC, IR and elemental analysis.

Chelate polymers. General procedure: Metal acetate (Cd^{II} chloride) and ligand BMADM were dissolved in minimum quantity (20–40 ml) of DMF separately in molar ratio 1 : 1. Both the solutions were filtered and mixed in hot condition. The mixture was refluxed on an oil-bath for 5 h. The coloured products obtained with different metals were washed successively with DMF, absolute ethanol and acetone, then dried at 80° and kept in vacuum desiccator over calcium chloride. The chelate polymers were insoluble in most of the solvents and could not be characterized by

NMR and solution electronic spectra

Metal and sulfur were determined by standard methods²⁰ C, H and N were analyzed at C D R I , Lucknow The magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature by Gouy's method Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a PAS photoacoustic spectrophotometer using BaSO₄ as calibrant and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer DC electrical conductivity was measured by voltage drop method using d c microvoltmeter in pellet form²¹

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